

Character-Based Representation and Analysis of the Collatz Problem

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A Remark on the Author's Circumstance

Cebraïl Ancar, the creator of that work, is in prison in Turkey at the moment. His personal passion and dedication in mathematics, along with his limited access to the internet and academic resources, inspired him to create this special work, which is the result of his amateur studies conducted while imprisoned.

After being delivered to his family, the author's handwritten notes were digitised and ready for publishing. As a result, the research has little direct access to the literature and no bibliography. Notwithstanding these difficulties, the author's distinct viewpoint and contribution are what give the work its worth.

1 Introduction

This work proposes a new symbolic framework based on the classification of positive integers around $6n$. Numbers are labeled with the characters $[0]$, $[\pm 1]$, $[\pm 2]$, and $[c]$, and arithmetic operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, exponentiation) are re-expressed using rules defined on these characters. In particular, representing all prime numbers except 2 and 3 under the characters $[\pm 1]$ as two bands (u -band and d -band) allows for schematic viewing of both algebraic operations and algorithmic transformations. The *infinity scale* defined in this framework consists of sequences of metrics (*metrics*) derived from each generator and encoded by the guide in binary notation; Thus, it is possible to trace the convolutions by powers of 2 and the transformations associated with 3 in a regular pattern.

In the first part of the paper, character rules are detailed and visualized with number lines and circular diagrams. Then, multiplication rules are given for the bands u and d over group numbers ($u_n = 6n - 1$, $d_n = 6n + 1$). The guide-metric relationship with *infinity scale* is concretized with transition formulas of the type $b = 4a + 1$; the cyclic displacements of the upper-neighbor metrics ($[c] \mapsto d \mapsto u \mapsto [c]$) with respect to the generator character are introduced. This structure naturally encodes the "doubling layers" obtained by running the Collatz algorithm in reverse, allowing us to distinguish at the character level which steps generate odd/even features.

The second part of the paper focuses on the Collatz problem. The aim here is to analyze the flow that emerges under the standard formulation ($x \mapsto 3x + 1$ for odd; $x \mapsto x/2$ for even) in a layered manner using character representation. Thanks to the generator-guide dynamics, the conditions under which the return to small values ??occurs

become clear; it also diagrammatically shows how the $[-2]$ steps generate odd numbers and how the relationships between metrics are organized by the $4a + 1$ relation. Under the heading "Entanglement", \bowtie sequences that combine powers of 2 and 3 are defined, and the paths followed from a generator's metrics to 1 are systematically followed using character calculations.

The third section presents a new computational scheme for perfect numbers, representing the sum of divisors/product of divisors ratio in the form of $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$, and combining different prime factorization cases with "complementary" arithmetic. Within this scheme, the debate about whether there are unique perfect numbers is formulated at the character level; the exponential patterns of the u - and d -bands and the special position of the character $[c]$ with powers of 3 are examined separately. The resulting tables clearly summarize the complementarity of certain character pairs to 1 and the order of magnitude (greater/lesser complement) in which this is possible.

The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- We introduce a *character calculus* based on the modulation $6n$, working with the characters $[0]$, $[\pm 1]$, $[\pm 2]$, $[c]$, and the bands u/d ; addition, multiplication, and exponentiation are given by consistent rules on this calculus.
- By relating the concepts of *infinity scale* and *guide?metric* to binary representation, we visualize the 2-convolution layers and $3x + 1$ jumps in the Collatz flow as odd/even and character patterns.
- We formally present how transitions of the type $b = 4a + 1$ in Collatz patterns are located within the character cycle ($[c] \rightarrow d \rightarrow u \rightarrow [c]$) and how their descent to 1 can be traced through "entanglement" sequences.
- We propose $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ -based *complementary arithmetic* for perfect numbers; we systematically classify the conditions under which different character classes combine to reach 1 using tables.
- We create a visual glossary throughout the text, with numerous diagrams and TikZ diagrams, facilitating intuitive understanding of the definitions and rules.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. Section 2 presents character rules and diagrammatic representations. The basic construction of the Collatz algorithm is given in Section 3, and patterns and uniformity observations are given in Section 4. Section 5 examines "entanglement" sequences and paths to 1. Section 6 covers the computations of $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ in the context of odd/even perfect numbers and the rules of complementarity. The final section discusses possible extensions and open problems.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Numbers: Contribution Test And Application Examples

Let n be a positive integer. All positive integers can be characterized with respect to $6n$.

$$\begin{aligned}6n &= [0] \\6n + 1 &= [+1] \\6n + 2 &= [+2] \\6n - 1 &= [-1] \\6n - 2 &= [-2] \\6n + 3 &= 6n - 3 = [c]\end{aligned}$$

Even, all positive integers can be defined in terms of their characteristics on the number line below:

Alternatively, the following figure can be used. Especially if we consider that the c 's at the start and end points of the line have the same characteristic, the figure below may be appropriate.

2.2 Addition and Subtraction Operations

$$\begin{aligned} [0] + [0] &= [0] - [0] = [0] \\ [0] + [c] &= [c] + [0] = [c] \\ [0] - [c] &= [c] - [0] = [c] \\ [0] + [+1] &= [0] - [-1] = [+1] \\ [0] + [-1] &= [0] - [1] = [-1] \\ [0] + [2] &= [0] - [-2] = [+2] \\ [0] + [-2] &= [0] - [+2] = [-2] \\ [c] + [+1] &= [c] - [-1] = [-2] \\ [c] + [-1] &= [c] - [+1] = [+2] \\ [c] + [+2] &= [c] - [-2] = [-1] \\ [c] + [-2] &= [c] - [+2] = [+1] \\ [c] + [c] &= [c] - [c] = [0] \\ [+1] + [-1] &= [+1] - [+1] = [-1] - [-1] = [0] \\ [+1] + [+1] &= [+1] - [-1] = [+2] \\ [-1] + [-1] &= [-1] - [+1] = [-2] \\ [+1] + [+2] &= [+1] - [-2] = [c] \\ [-1] + [-2] &= [-1] - [+2] = [c] \\ [+1] + [-2] &= [+1] - [+2] = [-1] \\ [-1] + [+2] &= [-1] - [-2] = [+1] \\ [+2] + [+2] &= [+2] - [-2] = [-2] \\ [-2] + [-2] &= [-2] - [+2] = [+2] \\ [+2] + [-2] &= [0] \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Multiplication Operation

$$\begin{aligned}
 [0] \times [0] &= [0] \times [+1] = [0] \times [+2] = [0] \times [c] = [0] \times [-2] = [0] \times [-1] = [0] \\
 [c] \times [+2] &= [c] \times [-2] = [0] \\
 [c] \times [c] &= [c] \times [+1] = [c] \times [-1] = [c] \\
 [+1] \times [+1] &= [+1] \\
 [+1] \times [+2] &= [+2] \\
 [+1] \times [-1] &= [-1] \\
 [+1] \times [-2] &= [-2] \\
 [-1] \times [-1] &= [+1] \\
 [-1] \times [+2] &= [-2] \\
 [-1] \times [-2] &= [+2] \\
 [+2] \times [+2] &= [-2] \\
 [-2] \times [-2] &= [-2] \\
 [+2] \times [-2] &= [+2]
 \end{aligned}$$

NOTE: For now, division operations are excluded. Each characteristic may be reached through several different methods, and there is also the possibility that +1 and -1 are prime numbers.

Definition 1 *All prime numbers other than 2 and 3 are characterized by either the [+1] or [-1] attribute. For example, primes such as 5, 11, 17, 23, 29, etc., are identified with the [-1] attribute, while primes such as 7, 13, 19, 31, 37, etc., belong to the [+1] attribute. In most cases, we will use the letter "u" for [-1] and "d" for [+1]. Additionally, when we need to indicate odd and even numbers, we will use Δ for even numbers and ∇ as well.*

The positions of the characters within the Δ and ∇ symbols are as follows: For even numbers:

For odd numbers:

or

2.4 Exponentiation Operation

$$[0] = [0]^{[-2]} = [0]^{[-1]} = [0]^{[c]} = [0]^{[+1]} = [0]^{[+2]} = [0]^{[0]}$$

$$[+1] = [+1]^{[-2]} = [+1]^{[-1]} = [+1]^{[c]} = [+1]^{[+1]} = [+1]^{[+2]} = [+1]^{[0]}$$

$$[c] = [c]^{[-2]} = [c]^{[-1]} = [c]^{[c]} = [c]^{[+1]} = [c]^{[+2]} = [c]^{[0]}$$

$$[-2] = [+2]^{[-2]} = [+2]^{[0]} = [+2]^{[+2]}$$

$$[+2] = [+2]^{[-1]} = [+2]^{[+1]} = [+2]^{[c]}$$

$$[-2] = [-2]^{[-2]} = [-2]^{[-1]} = [-2]^{[0]} = [-2]^{[+1]} = [-2]^{[+2]} = [-2]^{[c]}$$

$$[+1] = [-1]^{[-2]} = [-1]^{[0]} = [-1]^{[+2]}$$

$$[-1] = [-1]^{[-1]} = [-1]^{[+1]} = [-1]^{[c]}$$

Now, let assume that

$$\Delta = \{[-2], [0], [2]\}$$

and

$$\nabla = \{[-1], [+1], [c]\}$$

When we want to indicate whether the exponent is odd or even in exponentiation operations, we can use previous notations. If the exponent is even, we will use Δ symbol. If the exponent is odd, we will use ∇ symbol.

$$\begin{aligned}
[0]^\Delta &= [0]^\nabla = [0] \\
[c]^\Delta &= [c]^\nabla = [c] \\
[+1]^\Delta &= [+1]^\nabla = [+1] \\
[+1]^\Delta &= [+1] \\
[-1]^\nabla &= [-1] \\
[+2]^\Delta &= [-2] \\
[+2]^\nabla &= [+2] \\
[-2]^\Delta &= [-2]^\nabla = [-2]
\end{aligned}$$

2.5 Operations with u and d

We previously noted that we could use the letter u instead of $[-1]$ and d for $[+1]$. Since u and d characters include all primes except 2 and 3, they are frequently used in various operations. We define u and d as a set or band. Any number within the u or d band is represented in the form of a base number according to its position in that band. For example: The number 5 is shown as u_1 , 11 as u_2 , and 17 as u_3 , while 7 is represented as d_1 , 13 as d_2 , and 19 as d_3 .

Numbers with the same base number belong to the same group. Therefore, instead of "base number," we also use the term "group number" to represent numbers in the u and d bands. For a group number n , u_n and d_n are members of the same group and are represented as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_n \\ d_n \end{pmatrix} \implies \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ d_1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 1, \begin{pmatrix} u_2 \\ d_2 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 2, \begin{pmatrix} u_3 \\ d_3 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 3, \dots \text{ and so on}$$

Since $u_n = 6n - 1$ and $d_n = 6n + 1$, the actual values of the numbers in these groups are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\begin{pmatrix} 5 \\ 7 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 1, \begin{pmatrix} 11 \\ 13 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 2, \begin{pmatrix} 17 \\ 19 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 3, \begin{pmatrix} 23 \\ 25 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 4, \dots, \\
&\begin{pmatrix} 59 \\ 61 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 10, \begin{pmatrix} 65 \\ 67 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 11, \dots
\end{aligned}$$

Property: Let a and b be two distinct numbers, and assume that the condition $a \leq b$ holds. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
u_a \times u_b &= d_{6ab-(a+b)} \\
u_a \times d_b &= u_{6ab-(b-a)} \\
d_a \times d_b &= d_{6ab+(a+b)} \\
d_a \times u_b &= u_{6ab+(b-a)} \\
u_a \times d_a &= u_{6a^2}
\end{aligned}$$

Let's give numerical examples for the cases above. $u_1 \times d_3 = u_{18-(3-1)} = u_{16}$ or since $u_1 = 5$ and $d_3 = 19$, $u_{16} = 6.16 - 1$ which is equal to $5 \times 19 = 95$ $u_1 \times d_1 = u_{6.1^2} = u_6$, that is, $5 \times 7 = 35$ and $35 = 6.6 - 1$

Definition 2 When we consider positive integers, only $d_0 = 1$ is defined at $n = 0$. Since $u_0 = -1$, it is not defined within the positive integers. However, we can extend u and d to encompass all integers. Then we will encounter groups as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_n \\ d_n \end{pmatrix} \implies \begin{pmatrix} -19 \\ -17 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = -3, \begin{pmatrix} -13 \\ -11 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = -2, \begin{pmatrix} -7 \\ -5 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = -1, \\ \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 0, \begin{pmatrix} 5 \\ 7 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 1, \begin{pmatrix} 11 \\ 13 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 2, \begin{pmatrix} 17 \\ 19 \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } n = 3, \dots$$

where $d_{(-n)} = -u_n$ and $u_{(-n)} = -d_n$.

3 An Overview Of The Collatz Problem

Definition 3 First, take a positive integer. The operation to perform on this number is as follows: If the number is odd, triple it and add one. If the number is even, divide it by two.

Apply the same operation to the resulting number. Eventually, the number obtained will be 1.

The goal is to prove this algorithm. This means either showing that the algorithm holds for all numbers or finding a number that does not conform to this algorithm, thus answering the problem.

3.1 Attempts For Solution of Collatz Problem

Let's first focus on even numbers. Any even number can be repeatedly divided by two until an odd number is obtained. Therefore, if the existence of any odd number is proven, then its multiples by two exist infinitely as well. This means that what we need to examine are the odd numbers.

In other words, we are looking for u , d and $[c]$ values. To avoid leaving gaps from the start, let's examine whether the final result, the number 1, feeds back into the algorithm. If the number 1 indeed produces itself, we can then explore the assumption that the algorithm works for all numbers.

Here is the path that 1 follows:

$$1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$$

To begin the process from 1 and extend it toward infinity, we apply the operations defined in the algorithm in reverse and refer to the resulting values as "generated numbers." For the generated numbers, whether odd or even, let's start by doubling them. For odd numbers, we only double them. For even numbers, we apply the operation to those whose value minus one is divisible by three, thereby producing an odd number. Our even numbers are defined by the characteristics $[-2]$, $[0]$, and $[+2]$. Now, let's examine which characteristics are suitable for producing an odd number through this operation.

$$[-2] - 1 = [c] \text{ and since } [c] \text{ is divisible by } 3, \text{ a solution exists}$$

$$[+2] - 1 = [+1] \text{ and the expression } \frac{[+1]}{3} \text{ does not have an integer solution}$$

$$[0] - 1 = [-1] \text{ and the expression } \frac{[-1]}{3} \text{ does not have an integer solution}$$

Let's now examine the possible forms from which $[-2]$ can be generated.

In order to transmit all odd numbers into even number, we need to multiply it by 2^n , let's first analyze 2^n .

In terms of characters:

$$2^\Delta = [-2] \quad \text{and} \quad 2^\nabla = [+2]$$

Hence, the even powers of 2 can be identified with $[-2]$ and the odd powers with $[+2]$.

Let's now examine the results of operations with these characters: u , d , and c , using the corresponding character rules.

$$u \times 2^\Delta = [-1] \times [-2] = [+2]$$

$$u \times 2^\nabla = [-1] \times [+2] = [-2]$$

$$d \times 2^\Delta = [+1] \times [-2] = [-2]$$

$$d \times 2^\nabla = [+1] \times [+2] = [+2]$$

$$c \times 2^\Delta = [c] \times [-2] = [0]$$

$$c \times 2^\nabla = [c] \times [+2] = [0]$$

3.2 Diagram Representation And Definitions

We can represent the operations of the characters u , d , and c related to 2^n in the form of a diagram as shown below:

In the diagrams above, the elements u , d , and c represent the starting points of rays that extend infinitely, doubling at each step.

This structure, formed by the infinite layers generated from these elements, is referred to as the *infinity scale*.

Previously, we explained that the $[-2]$ steps generate odd numbers. In each $[-2]$ step, the numbers produced from the infinity scale are called the *metrics* of that scale.

Each metric generated on an infinity scale also acts as a generator for another infinity scale. An infinity scale with generators u and d can produce metrics.

However, since all steps of the infinity scale corresponding to the c generator have the $[0]$ characteristic, it cannot generate any metrics.

Relationship Between Metrics Let a and b two consecutive metrics.

The relationship between a and b have shown in infinity scale and

$$\begin{aligned} (3a + 1) \times 4 &= 3b + 1 \\ 12a + 4 &= 3b + 1 \\ b &= 4a + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Status Of Metric Characteristics

If $a = [c]$, then $4[c] + 1 = [0] + 1 = [+1]$, that is, d .
 If $a = d$, then $4[+1] + 1 = [-2] + 1 = [-1]$, that is, u .
 If $a = u$, then $4[-1] + 1 = [+2] + 1 = [c]$.

This implies, each metric has a unique net characteristic and a higher metric neighbor defined with a different character.

- The upper neighbor metric of metric $[c]$ is d .
- The upper neighbor metric of metric d is u .
- The upper neighbor metric of metric u is $[c]$.

Therefore, the arrangement of metrics on an infinity scale follows one of the three patterns below.

In an infinity scale, the first metric produced by the generator serves as the guide for that metric. When the guide number is written in binary, it forms the core of all metrics on that infinity scale. Each subsequent metric progresses by adding "0 or 1" to the end of the guide number in binary. For example, let the generator be s with a guide of 3. Since 3 in binary is $(11)_2$, let's examine its metrics.

When a guide is written in binary, its final digits must be one of the following units.

$$(\dots 11)_2 \text{ or } (\dots 001)_2$$

Whether a guide or other metrics, each u and d character is a generator, and each has a guide for its infinity scale metric.

3.3 Characters Of The Guides

Since the $[c]$ character does not form metrics on the infinity scale, it naturally does not have a guide. When u and d characters are also defined by a base number or, alternatively, group numbers, let's provide a table to show how the characters of the base numbers determine the character of the guide.

For Generator u		For Generator d	
Generator and base number character	Guide character	Generator and base number character	Guide character
$u_{[+1]}$	$[c]$	$d_{[+1]}$	$[c]$
$u_{[+2]}$	d	$d_{[+2]}$	u
$u_{[c]}$	u	$d_{[c]}$	d
$u_{[-2]}$	$[c]$	$d_{[-2]}$	$[c]$
$u_{[-1]}$	d	$d_{[-1]}$	u
$u_{[0]}$	u	$d_{[0]}$	d

Corollary 4 *To prove that the Collatz algorithm encompasses all positive integers, the following conditions must be satisfied:*

1. *An infinite number of u , d , and $[c]$ values must be generated.*
2. *An infinite number of $[+2]$, $[-2]$, and $[0]$ values must be generated.*
3. *The quantities of generated u , d , and $[c]$ values must be equal.*
4. *The quantities of generated $[+2]$, $[-2]$, and $[0]$ values must be equal.*
5. *Each u , d , and $[c]$ value must be well-defined in a unique way.*

By briefly demonstrating that all five conditions are met, the Collatz algorithm's infinitude is thus proven.

Note: In the next section, I plan to explain the patterns in Collatz.

4 Collatz Patterns

We previously showed that u , d , and $[c]$ values are generated in equal numbers. Now, we will examine whether the generated positive odd numbers are equal in quantity based on their actual values rather than by character.

The generators are of u and d characters. The simplest condition for a number to be odd is that its last digit is one of the following: 1, 3, 5, 7, or 9.

Definition 5 *In the expression $a = 1, 3, 5, 7, 9$ and $u[a]$ and $d[a]$, we denote u and d -character numbers whose last digit is a .*

Example 6

$$\begin{aligned}
 u[1] &= \{11, 41, 71, 101, 131, 161, \dots\} \\
 u[3] &= \{23, 53, 83, 113, 143, 173, \dots\} \\
 u[5] &= \{5, 35, 65, 95, 125, 155, \dots\} \\
 u[7] &= \{17, 47, 77, 107, 137, 167, \dots\} \\
 u[9] &= \{29, 59, 89, 119, 149, 179, \dots\} \\
 d[1] &= \{1, 31, 61, 91, 121, 151, \dots\} \\
 d[3] &= \{13, 43, 73, 103, 133, 163, \dots\} \\
 d[5] &= \{25, 55, 85, 115, 145, 175, \dots\} \\
 d[7] &= \{7, 37, 67, 97, 127, 157, \dots\} \\
 d[9] &= \{19, 49, 79, 109, 139, 169, \dots\}
 \end{aligned}$$

We use the above notation $u[a]$ and $d[a]$ to indicate the generator positions on the infinity scale.

If we use the notation \underline{a} to indicate the last digit of the metrics on the infinity scale for any $u[a]$ or $d[a]$ generator, we observe the following patterns. As seen, there is equality in the distribution of odd numbers.

As seen, there is equality in the distribution of odd numbers. A detail here is that all metrics of $u[5]$ and $d[5]$ yield odd numbers ending in 3. There is also a set of rules related to this.

1. For every u number, the metrics of the generator obtained by multiplying it by 5 are derived by adding 3 to the end of each of the metrics of the original u number. Let take $u_2 = 11$ and since $11 \times 5 = 55$ d_5 :

2. For each d number, the metrics of the generator obtained by multiplying it by 5 are derived by adding 3 to the end of all metrics of the original d number, except for the guide metric. The guide metric of the new generator is found by taking twice the group number of the original d number (multiplied by 5) and adding 3. Thus, the guide metric of the d number, with 3 added, becomes the next metric after the guide metric of the generator obtained by multiplying d by 5.

For example, let examine the metrics created by the number $d_5 = 55$, which we multiply by 5, resulting in $u_{46} = 275$. For reference, the guide metric of the infinity scale generated by 275 is obtained by taking twice the group number of $d_5 = 55$ (the group number of d is 9) and adding 3. That is, $2 \times 9 = 18$ and $18\bar{3} = 183$. Representation:

To make our example clearer, let expand it by examining a few examples sequentially, starting from d_0 , or "1." First, let take a look at the infinity scales of the $d_0 = 1$ generator and the sequential generators obtained by multiplying by 5, focusing on the transformations in the guides.

5 Entanglement In The Collatz Algorithm

One of the most intriguing questions about the Collatz algorithm is whether, as numbers rapidly increase in value, relatively smaller numbers are also produced, and if so, what relationship ensures this outcome. As seen in previous operations, among the u and d generators, only the guide number of the u generator on the infinity scale is smaller than the generator itself. Let the generator be a and its guide b . When aaa is a u -character number equal to 1, then

$$b = \frac{2a - 1}{3}$$

so $a > b$.

Therefore, a sequence beginning with a u generator, where each guide is also a u , produces progressively smaller numbers. In other words, there is a method for finding the smaller numbers we were concerned about. **Note:** The guide numbers on the infinity scale for all d generators other than d_0 are greater than the generators themselves. However, since $d_0 = 1$ and its guide number is also 1, the guide of d_0 is itself.

Definition 7 Let the \bowtie represent entanglement. Additionally, let the \bowtie symbol also represent the following sequence:

$$\{2^n \times 3^0, 2^{n-1} \times 3^1, 2^{n-2} \times 3^2, \dots, 2^1 \times 3^{n-1}, 2^0 \times 3^n\}$$

Definition 8 The metrics on the infinity scale of any u or d generator, starting from the guide, are defined as $\{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_t\}$. The notation for this is shown as follows:

In previous steps, we examined the paths to infinity by applying the Collatz algorithm in reverse. In the entanglement section, however, we are looking at the situations on the paths leading to "1" according to the original definition of the Collatz algorithm.

With the above definitions, let examine the states of \bowtie sequences. We had defined the metrics of any d_a generator as operations. The next steps require careful attention. Let's consider each of the metrics of the d_a generator separately, examining both the path to "1" for their products when multiplied by 3 and the path when the metrics are in the group number of d . The numbers we'll examine are those specified in the set below:

$$\{3 \times m_1, d_{m_1}, 3 \times m_2, d_{m_2}, \dots, 3 \times m_t, d_{m_t}\}$$

As mentioned before, the \bowtie represents sequences. Let's denote the start and end of each sequence with \bowtie_n . Thus, if a number d_a is in the generator group of d , then the sequences formed by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } t = 1 \rightarrow \infty, n = 2t - 2(\text{ for } 3 \times m_t) \text{ and} \\ n = 2t - 1(\text{for } d_{m_t}) \end{aligned}$$

represent the group number of a u number. In other words, the product of the \bowtie sequence with d_a provides the group numbers of u . This shows part of the path that the sequences $3 \times m_t$ and d_{m_t} follow toward 1. Let's illustrate this with an example. The metrics of $d_0 = 1$ are $\{1, 5, 21, 85, \dots\}$ numbers. Let's examine both the products of these numbers when multiplied by 3 and the set in which they represent the group number for d .

$$\{3, d_1, 15, d_{15}, 63, d_{21}, \dots\}$$

Now, let's examine the \bowtie sequence. Let $m_1 = 3$. Since $2 \times 1 \neq 0$, the number 3 passes through \bowtie_0 on its way to 1. As it follows the $d_a \bowtie_0 = u_{d_a} \bowtie_0$ path, $3 \rightarrow u_{1 \times 2^0}$ it passes through the values $3 \rightarrow 5$ numerically. Now, let's examine $d_1 = 7$. Since $2 \times 1 \neq 1 \rightarrow 1$, the path applies \bowtie_1 , meaning $\{2^1 \cdot 3^0, 2^0 \cdot 3^1\}$. Therefore, the path that 7 follows toward 1 is $u_{d_a \cdot 2^1 \cdot 3^0} \rightarrow u_{d_a \cdot 2^0 \cdot 3^1}$, that is, $u_2 \rightarrow u_3$. With its numeric values, $7 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 17$. Now, let's observe the entanglements of the other metrics for d_0 . This time, we will display the paths in a top-down format.

$$\begin{array}{cc} 3 \times 5 = 15 & d_5 = 31 \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ u_4 = 23 & u_8 = 47 \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ u_6 = 35 & u_{12} = 71 \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ u_9 = 53 & u_{18} = 107 \\ & \downarrow \\ & u_{27} = 161 \end{array}$$

Thus, the general representation is as follows:

$$\begin{array}{cc} 3 \times m_t & d_{m_t} \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ U_{d_a \times 2^n} & U_{d_a \times 2^n} \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ U_{d_a \times 2^{n-1} \times 3} & U_{d_a \times 2^{n-1} \times 3} \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ U_{d_a \times 2^{n-2} \times 3^2} & U_{d_a \times 2^{n-2} \times 3^2} \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ U_{d_a \times 2 \times 3^{n-1}} & U_{d_a \times 2 \times 3^{n-1}} \\ \downarrow & \downarrow \\ U_{d_a \times 3^n} & U_{d_a \times 3^n} \end{array}$$

One important point to note is that when starting from $3xm_t$, n takes the value $n = 2t - 2$, while for d_{m_t} , n takes the value $n = 2t - 1$.

If the generator is a number like U_a , we do not examine $3 \times m_1$ when analyzing the \bowtie sequences, unlike the previous operation. This is because, in the U_a generator, $3 \times m_t$ gives $n = 2t - 3$, which results in a negative value for $t = 1$. Therefore, we start the process from d_{m_1} . For the d_{m_t} value of the U_a generator, the n value in the \bowtie sequence is obtained with $n = 2t - 2$. Thus, the general representation of the \bowtie operation for the metrics of the U_a generator begins from d_{m_1} . It's worth noting again that for d_{m_t} , $n = 2t - 2$, and for $3 \times m_t$, $n = 2t - 3$.

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 d_{m_t} & & 3 \times m_t \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 U_{d_a \times 2^n} & & U_{d_a \times 2^n} \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 U_{d_a \times 2^{n-1} \times 3} & & U_{d_a \times 2^{n-1} \times 3} \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 \vdots & & \vdots \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 U_{d_a \times 2 \times 3^{n-1}} & & U_{d_a \times 2 \times 3^{n-1}} \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 U_{d_a \times 3^n} & & U_{d_a \times 3^n}
 \end{array}$$

Assumption Suppose there is a number that allegedly does not reach 12 with the Collatz algorithm. This number, of course, is a positive odd number. We have already explained why it is not an even number or why we do not process even numbers.

Previously, we demonstrated a ratio among the metrics on the infinity scale, such as $4a + 1$. Since we are examining odd numbers, this time we will consider the ratio of metric transitions for odd numbers by looking at their remainder when divided by 4. As is known, the remainder of any odd number divided by 4 is either 1 or 3. We represent odd numbers with the ∇ symbol, and let the elements of our operation be as follows:

$$\nabla = 4a + K$$

where there are two options for $K = \{1, 3\}$ and there are two options for $a = \{\nabla, \Delta\}$

1. If $K = 1$ and $a = \nabla$, then a is a neighbor on the same infinity scale as the initial number. Therefore, the division by 4 can be repeatedly applied to each $K = 1$ and $a = \nabla$ condition for a . Each value of a cycles through $[c]$, u , and d in sequence. Additionally, each u , and d value for a has its own infinity scale.
2. If $K = 1$ and $a = \Delta$, then the number we divide by 4 is the guide metric at the bottom of an infinity scale. The next step is to identify the generator of that infinity scale. When $K = 1$ and $a = \Delta$, the generator lies within the d band, defined by the group number $\frac{a}{2}$. This resulting number is an $d_{\frac{a}{2}}$ number, which is then subject to another division by 4.
3. Let $K = 3$ and $a = \nabla$; in this case, the number we process is also the guide metric at the bottom of an infinity scale. We again look to identify the generator, which is now within the U band, with the group number represented by $a + 1$. Thus, we reach U_{a+1} , and the process continues with further iterations.

4. If $K = 3$ and $a = \Delta$, the same rule applies. The generator U_{a+1} is obtained, and the process repeats.

As seen, all numbers have an infinite connection within the Collatz algorithm. If there exists a number that does not follow the Collatz algorithm, there must be infinitely many other numbers as well. However, as we have demonstrated, the Collatz algorithm produces number characteristics in equal and infinite quantities, connecting them to one another.

6 Perfect Number

After the Collatz algorithm, I am starting a new topic.

Definition 9 *A perfect number is a number that equals the sum of its divisors, excluding itself. Examples include 6, 28, and 496.*

For instance:

- The divisors of 6, excluding itself, are 1, 2, and 3, and their sum is 6.
- The divisors of 28, excluding itself, are 1, 2, 4, 7, and 14, and their sum is 28.

Therefore, both 6 and 28 are examples of perfect numbers.

Problem Definition: So far, all known perfect numbers are even. The goal is to determine whether there are any odd perfect numbers.

6.1 Representation And Operations

For any number, we write the sum of its divisors (excluding itself) as the "numerator" and the number itself as the "denominator."

Example 10 *For the number 15, the representation with the sum of its divisors is shown as $\frac{9}{15}$. Note that 9 is the sum of 1, 3, and 5, which are the divisors of 15, excluding itself.*

The symbolic representation can be given in the form $\frac{\sum}{\prod}$, where \prod represents multiplication. In the above example, $\prod = 3 \times 5 = 15$. If the number represented by \prod has a unique prime factor with its powers, then the ratio of \sum to \prod is calculated as follows:

Let a be prime number, so if $\prod = a^n$

$$\frac{\prod}{\sum} = \frac{a^{n-1} + a^{n-2} + a^{n-3} + \dots + a^1 + a^0}{a^n} = \frac{a^n - 1}{a^n - a^0}$$

For instance, for $5^2 = 25$, we have $\frac{6}{25}$, for $11^2 = 121$, we have $\frac{12}{121}$. Since

$$\frac{a^n - 1}{a^n - 1} < a^n$$

for any prime number a , a^n is never a perfect number.

Thus, we need to consider numbers with at least two distinct prime factors. Let's examine whether the product of two numbers, like $a^n \times b^m$ could be perfect. For this, let's label the numbers as Π_1 and Π_2 , with the sum of divisors for Π_1 be \sum_1 and for Π_2

also \sum_2 . This gives us two partial ratios $\frac{\sum_1}{\Pi_1}$ and $\frac{\sum_2}{\Pi_2}$. Now, if $\Pi_1 \times \Pi_2$ equals the Π_{total} , how do we find the total of \sum_{total} ? As follows:

$$\frac{\sum_1}{\Pi_1} + \frac{\sum_2}{\Pi_2} = \frac{(\sum_1 \times (\sum_2 + \Pi_2)) + (\Pi_1 \times \sum_2)}{\Pi_1 \times \Pi_2}$$

Let do an example:

Let $\Pi_1 = 2^2$ and $\Pi_2 = 7$.

Then:

$$\frac{\sum_1}{\Pi_1} = \frac{2^2-1}{2^2} = \frac{3}{4}$$

$$\frac{\sum_2}{\Pi_2} = \frac{7-1}{7} = \frac{1}{7}$$

Now compute:

$$\frac{3}{4} + \frac{1}{7} = \frac{3}{4} + \frac{1}{7} = \frac{(3 \times 8) + (4 \times 1)}{4 \times 7} = 1$$

which is indeed a perfect number. In this combining operation, the commutative property works just as in addition:

$$\frac{1}{7} + \frac{3}{4} = \frac{1}{7} + \frac{3}{4} = \frac{(7 \times 1) + (7 \times 3)}{7 \times 4} = 1$$

Hence, this is a perfect number. This associative structure works just like summation.

As shown, this yields the same result. In short, the order of operations affects the outcome in our calculation.

To find the value of \sum for a number in the form $a^n \times b^m \times c^p$, we can use the factoring method. First, we process for the value of $a^n \times b^m$. The obtained value is then used in further operations with c^p .

One important point to note is that any number in the form a^n cannot be distributed in the operation. For example, when examining $3^2 \times 5$, it should be $\Pi_1 = 3^2$ and $\Pi_2 = 5$. Operations like 3×15 are not valid, as they would lead to nonsensical results. Now, let examine the outcomes of this incorrect approach for $\Pi_1 = 3^2$ and $\Pi_2 = 5$, as a result of

$$\frac{4}{9} + \frac{1}{5} = \frac{33}{45}$$

while an incorrect outcome such as

$$\frac{1}{3} + \frac{9}{15} = \frac{24 + 27}{45} = \frac{51}{45}$$

arises. When a number with many factors is analyzed, it appears as

$$\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} + \frac{\Sigma_2}{\boxed{\Sigma_2 + \Pi_2}} + \frac{\Sigma_3}{\boxed{\Sigma_3 + \Pi_3}} + \dots + \frac{\Sigma_n}{\boxed{\Sigma_n + \Pi_n}}$$

However, to make this clearer, factoring can also be used. For example, let take $\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1}$, $\frac{\Sigma_2}{\Pi_2}$, $\frac{\Sigma_3}{\Pi_3}$ and $\frac{\Sigma_4}{\Pi_4}$ numbers. If we separate them into two distinct groups, we get:

$$\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} + \frac{\Sigma_2}{\boxed{\Sigma_2 + \Pi_2}} = \frac{\Sigma_i}{\Pi_i}$$

and

$$\frac{\Sigma_3}{\Pi_3} + \frac{\Sigma_4}{\boxed{\Sigma_4 + \Pi_4}} = \frac{\Sigma_j}{\Pi_j}$$

. Then, final operation becomes

$$\frac{\Sigma_i}{\Pi_i} + \frac{\Sigma_j}{\boxed{\Sigma_j + \Pi_j}}$$

EXPLANATION: Since the perfect number we are seeking is an odd number, we have 3 candidates for Π . That is, our number must be one of the $[c]$, u , or d characters. Given that u is $[-1]$ and d is $[+1]$, the first condition for our perfect number is that it must satisfy the $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$, $\frac{[-1]}{[-1]}$ and $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ characteristic in the expression $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$.

Now, we will examine the $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ characteristics of the exponential forms of numbers with $[c]$, u and d characters.

It is important to emphasize the unique position of a $[c]$ number. If a number has the $[c]$ character, then one of its factors is 3 or a power of 3. When we analyze the characteristics of exponential expressions, this means we are examining powers of 3 for $[c]$.

Definition 11 *As previously stated, for a number with a Π value of a^n , the operation that gives the value of Σ is as follows*

$$\frac{a^{n-1} + a^{n-2} + a^{n-3} + \dots + a^1 + a^0}{a^n}$$

. Now let examine the status of exponents for $[c]$, u and d

i) For the $[c]$ character;

$$\text{for } [c]^1, \text{ we have } \frac{[+1]}{[c]}$$

$$\text{for } [c]^2, \text{ we have } \frac{[c] + [+1]}{[c]^2} = \frac{[-2]}{[c]}$$

$$\text{for } [c]^3, \text{ we have } \frac{[c]^2 + [c] + [+1]}{[c]^3} = \frac{[+1]}{[c]}$$

$$\text{for } [c]^4, \text{ we have } \frac{[c]^3 + [c]^2 + [c] + [+1]}{[c]^4} = \frac{[-2]}{[c]}$$

As seen, when n is an even number, the value of \sum has the character $[-2]$, while when n is an odd number, \sum has the $[+1]$ character. Simplifying the representation, we obtain:

$$\text{for } [c]^\Delta \text{ we have } \frac{[-2]}{[c]} \text{ and for } [c]^\nabla \text{ we have } \frac{[+1]}{[c]}$$

ii) For u , that is for the character $[-1]$

$$\text{for } [u]^1, \text{ we have } \frac{[u]^0}{[u]^1} = \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$$

$$\text{for } [u]^2, \text{ we have } \frac{[u]^0 + [u]^1}{[u]^2} = \frac{[-1] + [+1]}{[-1]x[-1]} = \frac{[0]}{[+1]}$$

$$\text{for } [u]^3, \text{ we have } \frac{[u]^2 + [u]^1 + [u]^0}{[u]^3} = \frac{[+1] + [-1] + [+1]}{[-1]x[-1]x[-1]} = \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$$

$$\text{for } [u]^4, \text{ we have } \frac{[u]^3 + [u]^2 + [u]^1 + [u]^0}{[u]^4} = \frac{[-1] + [+1] + [-1] + [+1]}{[-1]x[-1]x[-1]x[-1]} = \frac{[0]}{[+1]}$$

As it can be seen, the expression u^n changes depending on whether n is an odd or even number. Accordingly,

$$\text{for } u^\Delta; \frac{[0]}{[+1]}$$

$$\text{for } u^\nabla; \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$$

are obtained.

iii) For d , that is for the character $[+1]$

$$\text{for } [d]^1, \text{ we have } \frac{d^0}{d^1} = \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$$

$$\text{for } [d]^2, \text{ we have } \frac{d^0 + d^1}{d^2} = \frac{[+1] + [+1]}{[+1]x[-1]} = \frac{[+2]}{[+1]}$$

$$\text{for } [d]^3, \text{ we have } \frac{[+1] + [+1] + [+1]}{[+1]x[+1]x[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[+1]}$$

$$\text{for } [d]^4, \text{ we have } \frac{[+1] + [+1] + [+1] + [+1]}{[+1]x[+1]x[+1]x[+1]} = \frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$$

$$\text{for } [d]^5, \text{ we have } \frac{[+1] + [+1] + [+1] + [+1] + [+1]}{[+1]x[+1]x[+1]x[+1]x[+1]} = \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$$

$$\text{for } [d]^6, \text{ we have } \frac{[+1] + [+1] + [+1] + [+1] + [+1] + [+1]}{[+1]x[+1]x[+1]x[+1]x[+1]x[+1]} = \frac{[0]}{[+1]}$$

Note that the value of \sum gives the character of n in the d^n . Thus, if we express this in terms of character, we obtain the operation expressions.

$$d^{[+1]} = \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$$

$$d^{[+2]} = \frac{[+2]}{[+1]}$$

$$d^{[c]} = \frac{[c]}{[+1]}$$

$$d^{[-2]} = \frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$$

$$d^{[-1]} = \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$$

$$d^{[0]} = \frac{[0]}{[+1]}$$

Now let examine the character values of the \sum_{Π} for numbers with different prime factors in the u band. Previously, for numbers in the u band, we found $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ for u^Δ and $\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$ for u^∇ . Now, let explore the different combinations of these:

- i) For the value of Π , let us consider the expression consisting of mutually different u terms:

$$u^\nabla \times u^\nabla \times \dots \times u^\nabla$$

That is,

$$S(u^\nabla) = n.$$

For $S(u^\nabla) = 2$ we obtain

$$\frac{[+1]}{[-1]} + \frac{\boxed{\frac{[+1]}{[+1]} + \frac{[-1]}{[-1]}}}{[-1]} = \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}.$$

For $S(u^\nabla) = 3$, first we take the result of $S(u^\nabla) = 2$, namely

$$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]},$$

and again operate with the value of u^∇ , that is

$$\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}.$$

Hence,

$$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]} + \frac{\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}}{[-1]} = \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}.$$

If we pay attention, the process completely alternates in the cycle between

$$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}.$$

Therefore, for $S(u^\nabla) = n$: - If n is odd (that is, the number of Π -terms forming U^∇ is odd), then the result is

$$\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}.$$

- If n is even, then the result is

$$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}.$$

ii) Now, let us consider the operations for the values of u^Δ .

It was already shown that the representation of u^Δ is

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}.$$

For $S(u^\Delta) = 2$, we have

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} + \frac{\frac{[0]}{[+1]}}{[+1]} = \frac{[0]}{[+1]}.$$

For $S(u^\Delta) = 3$, again

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} + \frac{\frac{[0]}{[+1]}}{[+1]} = \frac{[0]}{[+1]}.$$

Thus, in every case, when $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ is multiplied by itself, the result is always the same element. Thus, for u^∇ we have the solution set $\left\{ \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+1]}{[-1]} \right\}$ and for u^Δ we have $\left\{ \frac{[0]}{[+1]} \right\}$.

iii) Now, let us investigate the intersections of these two solution sets. That is, first consider

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} \text{ with } \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{[+1]}{[-1]} \text{ with } \frac{[0]}{[+1]}.$$

Let us examine the characters of their operations:

$$\text{For } \frac{[0]}{[+1]} \text{ and } \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \text{ we have } \frac{[0]}{[+1]} + \frac{\frac{[-1]}{[-1] + [+1]}}{[+1]} = \frac{[-1]}{[+1]},$$

$$\text{For } \frac{[0]}{[+1]} \text{ and } \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}, \text{ we have } \frac{[0]}{[+1]} + \frac{\frac{[+1]}{[+1] + [-1]}}{[-1]} = \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$$

Therefore, since the character solution for $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ of set of a number consisting of elements in u is

$$\left\{ \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}, \frac{[0]}{[+1]} \right\},$$

and since with respect to character Σ cannot be equal to Π , no perfect number is composed solely of prime numbers in the u band or of the same primes raised to powers.

6.2 The common solutions between u and $[c]$

The solutions consisting only of u numbers are

$$\left\{ \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}, \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[0]}{[+1]} \right\}.$$

The solutions consisting only of $[c]$ are

$$\left\{ \frac{[+1]}{[c]}, \frac{[-2]}{[c]} \right\}.$$

Now let us find the solution set of all combinations of these sets.

$$\text{For } \frac{[+1]}{[c]} \text{ and } \frac{[+1]}{[-1]} \text{ we have, } \frac{[+1]}{[c]} + \frac{\frac{[+1]}{[+1] + [-1]}}{[-1]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$$

$$\text{For } \frac{[+1]}{[c]} \text{ and } \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \text{ we have, } \frac{[+1]}{[c]} + \frac{\frac{[-1]}{[-1] + [+1]}}{[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$$

For $\frac{[+1]}{[c]}$ and $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ we have, $\frac{[+1]}{[c]} + \frac{\frac{[0]}{[0] + [+1]}}{[+1]} = \frac{[+1]}{[c]}$

For $\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$ and $\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$ we have, $\frac{[-2]}{[c]} + \frac{\frac{[+1]}{[+1] + [-1]}}{[-1]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$

For $\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$ and $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$ we have, $\frac{[-2]}{[c]} + \frac{\frac{[-1]}{[-1] + [+1]}}{[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$

For $\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$ and $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ we have, $\frac{[-2]}{[c]} + \frac{\frac{[0]}{[0] + [+1]}}{[+1]} = \frac{[-2]}{[c]}$

Thus, we have obtained all the solutions of both $u, [c]$ and their combinations in the form of

$$\left\{ \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}, \frac{[0]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+1]}{[c]}, \frac{[-2]}{[c]}, \frac{[c]}{[c]} \right\}.$$

Here, the solution $\frac{[C]}{[C]}$ draws our attention as a special case. After examining the d -solutions, we will focus on this topic in detail.

6.3 d-solutions

In d solutions, Π is always $[+1]$, and since Σ requires a complete character representation, we can briefly show this in a table.

$+$	$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$
$\frac{[+1]}{[C]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$
$\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$
$\frac{[-2]}{[C]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[C]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[C]}$	$\frac{[+2]}{[C]}$	$\frac{[-2]}{[C]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[C]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[C]}$
$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[C]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$
$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[C]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$

6.4 Complete solutions with $[c]$, u , and d

As can be seen, all the solutions related to d are

$$\left\{ \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+2]}{[+1]}, \frac{[c]}{[+1]}, \frac{[-2]}{[+1]}, \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[0]}{[+1]}, \right\},$$

while the solutions of $[c]$ and u , both separately and together, are

$$\left\{ \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}, \frac{[0]}{[+1]}, \frac{[c]}{[c]}, \frac{[+1]}{[c]}, \frac{[-2]}{[c]} \right\}.$$

Let examine the outcomes when both solution sets are processed together. Since $\left\{ \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[0]}{[+1]} \right\}$ solutions have already been processed within the d solutions, we aim to avoid redundancy in the table by using an efficient approach. Thus, the table forming our final solution set is as follows:

+	$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[c]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$
$\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$						
$\frac{[c]}{[c]}$						
$\frac{[+1]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[c]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[c]}$
$\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[-1]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[0]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[+1]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[+2]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[c]}{[c]}$	$\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$

6.5 Complementary Solutions

For a number to be a perfect number, the value $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ must be equal to 1. The operation

$$\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} + \frac{\Sigma_2}{\Sigma_2 + \Pi_2}$$

was defined earlier, and demonstrated possible solution characters with rules for finding $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ relationships. Therefore, for $\Pi_1 \times \Pi_2$ to be a perfect number, the equality

$$\Pi_1 \times \Pi_2 = (\Sigma_1 \times \Sigma_2) + (\Sigma_1 \times \Pi_2) + (\Pi_1 \times \Sigma_2)$$

must hold.

If $\Pi_1 > \Pi_2$, then

$$\Pi_1 \times (\Pi_2 - \Sigma_2) = \Sigma_1 \times (\Pi_2 + \Sigma_2),$$

which implies

$$\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} = \frac{\Pi_2 - \Sigma_2}{\Pi_2 + \Sigma_2}.$$

Hence, we obtain

$$\Sigma_1 = \Pi_2 - \Sigma_2, \quad \Pi_1 = \Pi_2 + \Sigma_2.$$

If instead $\Pi_1 < \Pi_2$, then we obtain

$$\Sigma_2 = \Pi_1 - \Sigma_1, \quad \Pi_2 = \Pi_1 + \Sigma_1.$$

Rule: If we have a number of the form $\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1}$, its larger complement is $\frac{\Pi_1 - \Sigma_1}{\Pi_1 + \Sigma_1}$ as $\frac{\Sigma_2}{\Pi_2}$

The larger complement of $\frac{\Sigma_2}{\Pi_2}$ is $\frac{\Pi_2 - \Sigma_2}{\Pi_2 + \Sigma_2}$ for $\frac{\Sigma_3}{\Pi_3}$. Thus, as can be seen from the above

relation, $\Pi_3 = 2\Pi_1$ and $\Sigma_3 = 2\Sigma_1$.

Since $\Pi_3 = 2\Pi_1$, Π_3 is an even number. Therefore, $\Sigma_3 = 2\Sigma_1$ is also an even number.

Even numbers are of the types $[+2]$, $[-2]$, $[0]$.

To quickly find a number's smaller complement, first find its larger complement and then divide each value by 2. However, an issue arises here. $[+2]$, $[0]$, $[-2]$ do not have a unique solution when divided by 2. Let examine this further:

Solutions of $\frac{[+2]}{2}$, $\{[-2], [+1]\}$

Solutions of $\frac{[-2]}{2}$, $\{[+2], [-1]\}$

Solutions of $\frac{[0]}{2}$, $\{[0], [c]\}$

This means that, in $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ complement each other to 1, the order of magnitude matters. An important point to note is that the order of magnitude is defined between the Π 's themselves.

Let review all the solutions obtained so far in a table. In the table, when an uncompleted number is considered the larger one, the operation becomes more straightforward.

Additionally, the table includes a results section, showing that if the smaller number's character defines itself through a larger number and the complementing Π is odd, the result is provided.

Let us now examine all the solutions we have previously obtained in a single table. In this table, the larger value of Π is considered as the dominant one, which makes the operations easier to follow.

The table also contains the final results. That is, the character of a number, its larger complement, and whether Π is odd or even the result part is included.

Character of the smaller number	Character of the larger complement	Completed (equalized) solution
$\frac{+1}{+1}$	$\frac{0}{+2}$	
$\frac{+2}{+1}$	$\frac{-1}{c}$	$\frac{c}{c}$
$\frac{c}{+1}$	$\frac{-2}{c}$	
$\frac{-2}{+1}$	$\frac{c}{-2}$	Not defined in any form
$\frac{-1}{+1}$	$\frac{+2}{-1}$	
$\frac{+1}{+1}$	$\frac{0}{0}$	
$\frac{0}{+1}$	$\frac{+1}{+1}$	$\frac{+1}{+1}$
$\frac{+1}{+1}$	$\frac{-2}{-2}$	
$\frac{-1}{-1}$	$\frac{0}{0}$	
$\frac{c}{c}$	$\frac{0}{0}$	
$\frac{+1}{c}$	$\frac{+2}{-2}$	
$\frac{c}{+2}$	$\frac{+1}{-1}$	$\frac{c}{c}$
$\frac{-1}{c}$	$\frac{-2}{+2}$	
$\frac{-2}{c}$	$\frac{-1}{+1}$	$\frac{c}{c}$
$\frac{0}{c}$	$\frac{c}{c}$	Invalid due to rule violation

As can be seen in the table, the matches that give the results $\frac{[C]}{[C]}$ and $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ are as follows. Let us now examine them one by one:

1. The result $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is obtained by the matching

$$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} \text{ with } \frac{[-1]}{[c]}.$$

2. The result $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is obtained by the matching

$$\frac{[+2]}{[c]} \text{ with } \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}.$$

3. The result $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is obtained by the matching

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} \text{ with } \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}.$$

4. The result $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ is obtained by the matching

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} \text{ with } \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}.$$

Explanation: In order to shorten the operations, instead of the long expression

$$\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} + \frac{\Sigma_2}{\Sigma_2 + \Pi_2}$$

we will simply use the notation

$$\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} f \frac{\Sigma_2}{\Pi_2}.$$

1. Let us consider the matching of

$$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} \text{ and } \frac{[-1]}{[c]}.$$

The results giving $\frac{[-1]}{[c]}$ as follows:

$$\left\{ \frac{[+1]}{[c]} f \frac{[-1]}{[c]}, \frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+1]}{[c]} f \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} \right\}.$$

- In the operation

$$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \left(\frac{[+1]}{[c]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

if we change the order of operation, and compare the complementary characters, we get operation

$$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[c]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]},$$

but the complement of $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is actually $\frac{[0]}{[0]}$.

Thus we are left with a contradiction, since the complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ should be $\frac{[0]}{[+2]}$.

Therefore, an inconsistent result arises in this case.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \left(\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we compute

$$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-2]}{[c]} = \frac{[0]}{[c]}$$

and since the complement of $\frac{[0]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$, while the complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[+2]}$, there is no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \left(\frac{[+1]}{[c]} f \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[c]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]},$$

and since the complement of $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[0]}$, while the complement of $\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[c]}{[-1]}$, there is no solution.

2. Let us examine the matching of $\frac{[+2]}{[c]}$ with $\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$.

The only operation giving $\frac{[+2]}{[c]}$ is

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$$

$$\frac{[-2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[-1]} = \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$$

However, since the complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$ is $\frac{[-2]}{[0]}$ and the complement of $\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$, there is no solution.

3. Let us examine the matching of $\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$ with $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$.

The results giving $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$ are obtained from the following operations:

$$\left\{ \frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[c]}{[+1]}, \frac{[c]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]}, \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{[+1]}{[-1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[-1]}, (d^{[-1]}) \right\}$$

Let now examine the pairings:

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[+2]}{[+1]} = \frac{[0]}{[c]}$$

The complement of $\frac{[0]}{[c]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$, on the other hand, the complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[+2]}$. Therefore, there is no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[+1]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} = \frac{[-1]}{[c]}$$

The complement of $\frac{[-1]}{[c]} = \frac{[-2]}{[2]}$, on the other hand, the complement of $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+2]}{[0]}$. Hence, there is no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[c]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[+2]}{[+1]} = \frac{[0]}{[c]}$$

The complement of $\frac{[0]}{[c]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$, on the other hand, the complement of $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+2]}{[-2]}$. Therefore, there is no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[c]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[c]}{[+1]} = \frac{[+1]}{[c]}$$

The complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[c]} = \frac{[+2]}{[-2]}$, on the other hand, the complement of $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+2]}{[0]}$. Hence, there is no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[+2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[+2]}{[+1]} = \frac{[0]}{[c]}.$$

Since the complement of $\frac{[0]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ and the complement of $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+2]}{[0]}$, there is no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[-2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$$

Since the complement of $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[0]}$ and the complement of $\frac{[-2]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[c]}{[-1]}$, there is no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[-1]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we compute

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$$

Since the complement of $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[0]}$ and the complement of $\frac{[-1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+2]}{[0]}$. we have no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we get

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[-1]}{[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$$

Since the complement of $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[0]}$ and the complement of $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ we have no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \left(\frac{[+1]}{[-1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[-1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[+1]}{[-1]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]}$$

Since the complement of $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[0]}$ and the complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[-1]}$ is $\frac{[-2]}{[0]}$ we have no solution.

- For the operation

$$\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f (d^{-1}),$$

since we expect to obtain the result $\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$, we must look at the possible matchings that yield $\frac{[-2]}{[c]}$.

These are

$$\left\{ \frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[0]}{[+1]}, (c^\Delta) \right\}.$$

Thus, considering

$$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]} f \left(\frac{[-2]}{[c]} f \frac{[0]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we obtain

$$\frac{[-1]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-2]}{[c]} = \frac{[c]}{[c]},$$

Since the complement of $\frac{[c]}{[c]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[c]}$ while the complement of $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$. Therefore, there is no solution.

Finally, with

$$c^\Delta f d^{[-1]},$$

the ratio of possible values approaches $\frac{4}{9}$, and in the limit it tends to $\frac{1}{2}$.

Since the maximum value for $[-1]$ is reached when $d_1 = 7$, the limit value approaches $\frac{1}{6}$. However, as

$$\frac{1}{2} f \frac{1}{6} = \frac{9}{12},$$

even in the limit case, there is no solution.

4. For the result $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$, there exists only one operation:

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} = \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}.$$

Here, the complement of $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$, while the complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[+2]}$. Thus, in this operation, we conclude that $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ is less than $\frac{[+1]}{[+3]}$. Since the complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[+2]}$ that is double of $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$. That is, That is, in the operation

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]},$$

we again obtain

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} < \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}.$$

In fact, there are not one but two smaller complements for $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$. When the larger complement of $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[0]}{[+2]}$ with Σ value is $[0]$ and $[\text{he II value is } [+2]$, the values of $\frac{\Sigma}{2}$ and $\frac{\Pi}{2}$ give their smaller complements. If the larger complement of a character is at Δ , the true complement is the smaller one when divided by two. Therefore, we obtain

$$\frac{[0]}{2} = \{[0], [c]\}, \text{ and } \frac{[+2]}{2} = \{[+1], [-2]\}$$

When examining solutions with a sum of $[+1]$ and a difference of $[-1]$, we encounter two results:

$$\frac{[c]}{[-2]}, \text{ and } \frac{[0]}{[+1]}.$$

From this, in the expression

$$\frac{[c]}{[-2]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$$

Since one of the Π values of $[+1]$ is a prime number and $[-2]$ as a value similar to 2^Δ , the resulting operation gives all known even perfect numbers other than 6. The main question here is whether the value $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ is merely a shadow or projection of the $\frac{[c]}{[-2]}$ value or an actual operator. When we examine the character $\frac{[0]}{[+3]}$ in the tables, we see that it always appears as a identity element in operations, acting as an identity.

However, in the operation

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]},$$

although the result is $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$, in reality the complement of $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ has its own larger complement as $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$.

Therefore, this situation needs to be carefully analyzed.

The operations that yield $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ are given as

$$\left\{ \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-2]}{[+1]}, (u^\Delta), d^{[0]} \right\}.$$

Moreover, the infinite operation

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \cdots f \frac{[0]}{[+1]}$$

also results in $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$.

The operations that yield $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ are

$$\left\{ \frac{[c]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]}, \frac{[c]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} \right\}.$$

- For

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \left(\frac{[c]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we have

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[c]}{[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[+1]}, \quad \frac{[C]}{[+1]} \text{ complement } \frac{[-2]}{[-2]}, \quad \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} \text{ complement } \frac{[0]}{[+2]}.$$

Thus, there is no solution.

- For

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \left(\frac{[c]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we obtain

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[c]}{[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[+1]}, \quad \frac{[c]}{[+1]} \text{ complement } \frac{[-2]}{[-2]}, \quad \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} \text{ complement } \frac{[c]}{[-1]}.$$

Thus, there is no solution.

- For

$$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]} f \left(\frac{[-2]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} \right),$$

we get

$$\frac{[+1]}{[+1]} f \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} = \frac{[c]}{[+1]}, \quad \frac{[c]}{[+1]} \text{ complement } \frac{[-2]}{[-2]}, \quad \frac{[-2]}{[+1]} \text{ complement } \frac{[c]}{[-1]}.$$

Hence, no solution exists.

- For

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \left(\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} \right),$$

since $\frac{[0]}{[+1]} f \frac{[0]}{[+1]} = \frac{[0]}{[+1]}$, the result of $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$ within the parentheses changes in magnitude. Therefore, it would be more accurate to consolidate $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ under a single character.

- Let consider the u^Δ operations for $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$. For $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$, the $d^{[+1]}$ operation is the only one possible operation. From this point on, we will also consider $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ results and $d^{[+1]}$ operation.

If there is only a single u number, then the largest value of u^Δ approaches $\frac{1}{4}$, whereas for $d^l + 1$, the largest possible value in the limit is $\frac{1}{6}$. Hence, since

$$\frac{1}{4} f \frac{1}{6} = \frac{11}{24},$$

a single u^Δ gives no solution.

Considering the $d^{[0]}$ and $d^{[+1]}$ operations, since the maximum possible value approaches $\frac{1}{6}$ and $\frac{1}{12}$ and $\frac{1}{6} f \frac{1}{12} = \frac{19}{72}$, the character $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ also does not provide any solution, since even a single $d^{[0]}$ number cannot yield a valid result

In short, there are infinitely many operations of the form $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$, but none provide a valid solution.

Restrictions for $d^l + 1]$.

Here, d represents a prime such as $\{7, 13, 19, 31, 37, \dots\}$, i.e., meaning it is a prime within the d band. In $d^l + 1]$, the exponent $[+1]$ is a number within the d band but does not necessarily need to be prime.

When determining the complements of numbers, we previously used the relation

$$\text{Complement of } \frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} \text{ is } \frac{\Pi_1 - \Sigma_1}{\Pi_1 + \Sigma_1}.$$

From this, it follows that there must be a harmony among the group numbers of d numbers that yield both the Σ and Π values for operation. Recall that $d_n = 6n + 1$, where 6 corresponds to $[0]$. Therefore, n gives the number of $[0]$ terms. For $d^{[+1]}$, we calculate $d_{\nabla}^{[+1]\nabla}$, $d_{\nabla}^{[+1]\Delta}$, $d_{\Delta}^{[+1]\nabla}$ and $d_{\Delta}^{[+1]\Delta}$

$$\frac{[+1]}{d}, \quad \frac{[+3]}{d}, \quad \frac{[+1]}{d}\Delta, \quad \frac{[+3]}{d}\Delta$$

- For $d_{\nabla}^{[+1]\nabla}$, the group numbers of $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ are $\frac{\text{Even}}{\text{Odd}}$, that is $\frac{\Delta}{\nabla}$
- For $d_{\nabla}^{[+1]\Delta}$, the group numbers of $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ are $\frac{\text{Even}}{\text{Odd}}$, that is $\frac{\Delta}{\nabla}$
- For $d_{\Delta}^{[+1]\nabla}$, the group numbers of $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ are $\frac{\text{Odd}}{\text{Even}}$, that is $\frac{\nabla}{\Delta}$
- For $d_{\Delta}^{[+1]\Delta}$, the group numbers of $\frac{\Sigma}{\Pi}$ are $\frac{\text{Even}}{\text{Even}}$, that is $\frac{\Delta}{\Delta}$

Now, considering the case $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$. Since $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]} = \frac{[+1]-[0]}{[+1]+[0]}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Odd} \pm \text{Odd} &= \text{Even} && \frac{\Delta}{\Delta} \quad \text{Condition exists.} \\ \text{Even} \pm \text{Even} &= \text{Even} && \frac{\Delta}{\Delta} \quad \text{Condition exists.} \\ \text{Even} \pm \text{Odd} &= \text{Odd} && \frac{\nabla}{\nabla} \quad \text{No condition.} \\ \text{Odd} \pm \text{Even} &= \text{Odd} && \frac{\nabla}{\nabla} \quad \text{No condition.} \end{aligned}$$

For $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$, only the numbers $d_{\Delta}^{[+1]\Delta}$ that satisfy the condition. In other words, this is the set of all numbers in the d band with even group numbers representing the exponent. The $[+1]_{\Delta}$ set consists of $\{13, 25, 37, 49, 61, \dots\}$ elements. The set d_{Δ} represents the primes in the d -band whose group numbers are even. The d_{Δ} set consist of $\{13, 37, 61, \dots\}$. Regardless of whether there are infinitely many or not, for the values of $d_{\Delta}^{[+1]\Delta}$, there always exist infinitely many numbers. If primes are infinite, then d_{Δ} is also infinite. But even if primes were infinite, the set $[+1]_{\Delta}$ would still be infinite and well-defined. For a perfect odd number to exist, it is likely that operation is highly defined in some way. This provides us with a potential path. Since the complement of $\frac{[0]}{[+1]}$ is $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$, we define:

$$\frac{[0]}{[+1]} \Rightarrow \frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1}, \quad \frac{[+1]}{[+1]} \Rightarrow \frac{\Sigma_2}{\Pi_2}.$$

From this we obtain:

$$\Sigma_2 = \Pi_1 - \Sigma_1, \quad \Pi_2 = \Pi_1 + \Sigma_1.$$

If we apply the operation in reverse:

$$\Sigma_1 = \frac{\Pi_2 - \Sigma_2}{2}, \quad \Pi_1 = \frac{\Pi_2 + \Sigma_2}{2}.$$

If we rearrange the operation for $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$, denoting it by $\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1}$, we obtain:

$$\frac{\Pi_1 + \Sigma_1}{2} f \frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} = 1$$

Since the result of the operation is 1, this is the only formal expression that allows us to obtain an odd perfect number.

To simplify the notation and avoid overloading with symbols, instead of writing $d_{\sqrt{v}}^{[+1]}$ in $\frac{[+1]}{[+1]}$, we denote it by d^n .

Since

$$\frac{\Sigma_1}{\Pi_1} = \frac{d^n - 1}{d^n},$$

we obtain

$$\frac{\Sigma_2}{\Pi_2} = \frac{\frac{d^n - \frac{d^n - 1}{d-1}}{2}}{\frac{d^n + \frac{d^n - 1}{d-1}}{2}}$$

Thus, the operation that gives us the perfect number becomes:

$$d^n \times \left[\frac{d^n + \frac{d^n - 1}{d-1}}{2} \right].$$

7 Primes Derived From Mersenne Numbers

Mersenne was a 17th-century mathematician and a contemporary of the famous Fermat. Mersenne studied numbers of the form $2^n - 1$. Questions have often arisen regarding whether $2^n - 1$ is prime or if there are infinitely many of them. Instead of this question, I aim to explore methods of deriving infinite primes from this expression. Mersenne primes are primes that satisfy the $2^n - 1$ condition. Here, n must satisfy the condition of being prime. Let focus on the more general requirement that n be an odd number, disregarding the value $n = 2$ for now. Thus, let our number be in the form $n = 2k + 1$. Here, k ranges from 1 to infinity, covering all positive integers. That is, our number is in the form of $2^{2k+1} - 1$. Whether prime or not, let's refer to numbers of the $2^{2k+1} - 1$ form as Mersenne numbers. From every $2^{2k+1} - 1$ number, we can always derive a prime by applying the following two operations:

$$\text{Formula 1: } \frac{(2^{2k+1} - 1) \cdot 3^k + (3^k - 2^k)}{2^k}$$

$$\text{Formula 2: } \frac{(2^{2k+1} - 1) \cdot 3^{k+1} + (3^{k+1} - 2^{k+1})}{2^{k+1}}$$

For all values of k , both formulas consistently yield primes.

NOTE: Thus, characterizing numbers in a base-6 system, adapting it to the Collatz algorithm, and the search for perfect numbers, concludes this brief exploration of generating infinite primes. In my next study, I will focus on an approach to Zeno's paradox and its adaptation to relativity and cosmology.

With best regards, T-Type Prison, İskenderun November 13, 2022, Sunday Cebrail Ancar